

Analyzing Behaviour of the Utilization of the Online News Clipping Database: Experience in Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University

Siriporn Poolsuwan, Kanyarat Bussaban

Abstract—This research aims to investigate and analyze user's behaviour towards the utilization of the online news clipping database at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Thailand. Data is gathered from 214 lecturers and 380 undergraduate students by using questionnaires. Findings show that most users knew the online news clipping service from their friends, library's website and their teachers. The users learned how to use it by themselves and others learned by training of SSRU library. Most users used the online news clipping database one time per month at home and always used the service for general knowledge, up-to-date academic knowledge and assignment reference. Moreover, the results of using the online news clipping service problems include the users themselves, service management, service device- computer and tools – and the network, service provider, and publicity. This research would be benefit for librarians and teachers for planning and designing library services in their works and organization.

Keywords—Online Database, User Behaviour.

I. INTRODUCTION

COUNTRIES around the world, including Thailand, are currently changing and developing themselves to achieve global competitiveness and to become knowledge-based societies in order to compete economically, politically, socially, scientifically, educationally, and technologically. Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University (SSRU) regarded as a fundamental source of wisdom will guide the country in the right direction. Therefore, it is inevitably necessary for SSRU to develop and improve the education and teaching systems to cope with the rapid and harsh changes. [1] In addition, the primary mission of Suan Sunandha Academic Resource Center (SARC) is serving the resource to support teaching and learning for students and university staffs. The mission is to provide the best education for our students and provide them become various powerful resources for their future employment and within the community. SSRU's core policy is based on The Education Act of 1999 [2], which focuses on the needs of students. All students have encouraged to practice self-learning, as this will help them adapt to change and lead them to lifetime achievements and successes. Therefore, SARC is designed to support those students, staff and teachers

S. Poolsuwan is with Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, 1 U-tong Nok Road, Dusit District, Bangkok, 10300, Thailand (e-mail: siriporn.po@ssru.ac.th)

K.Bussaban is with Faculty of Science and Technology, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, 1 U-tong Nok Road, Dusit District, Bangkok, 10300, Thailand (e-mail: kanyarat.bu@ssru.ac.th).

for self-learning. Updates are SARC top priority. With the power of the internet, the automatic library, the research staff, and other academic service, SARC would like to assist all departments to stay up to date with the rest of the world. [3]

Pressures on the budget of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University (SSRU) have resulted in an increasing focus on the development of quantitative of the SARC service. Because of a big part of the budget on fast electronics, they are ready for use within the center in order to provide positive learning environment for all users.

The purpose of this research was to investigate and analyze students and staff's behaviour in the utilization of the news clipping online database at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, and to see if any trouble shooting is needed to be done.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Online News Clipping Service at SSRU

Clipping is important and interesting news which is cut from newspapers, journals, magazines, or other documents that are useful for users. Each article is sealed on paper. Information description such as the publication name, page number and subject heading is written on the top of the clipping. [4] Clipping is kept in cabinets by its title. Moreover, online news clipping is an electronic clipping, and online news clipping can be accessed through the internet.

There are several services provided at SARC, such as: Internet, Journals and Newspapers, Audio and visual aids, Books, Reference service and online database: e-books, e-learning, including e-journals and e-encyclopedias and online news clipping. [5] Now, news clipping is a growing trend online, and we have that access in addition to our current library. Users can search online for anything, and at anytime. SARC has an online database including news, interviews, essays, critiques and reviews plus reports and analytical passages. It consists of 27 newspaper brands, starting from 1996. There are 10 million news clippings within SARC database [3]. These clippings are provided for our users without any charge, so our users can get benefit from all sources.

B. Materials and Methods

University is an institution of higher education and research which grants academic degrees in a variety of subjects and provides both undergraduate education and postgraduate

education [1]. The mission of the university is to provide education, to conduct research, to serve the society, and to conserve our culture. But now, knowledge has taken on a competitive role in the society, economies, and politics of several countries. Consequently, the traditional role for higher education is changing. A model of the university as a 'Knowledge University' is becoming increasingly accepted internationally. The university, therefore, aims to use its resources to further economic and social development [6].

In this research, 578 teachers and 32,742 undergraduate students enrolled in the first semester of 2012 are used as samples in this study. Students are from Faculty of Education, Faculty of Industrial Technology, Faculty of Humanities and Social Science, Faculty of Innovation and Management, Faculty of Science and Technology, Faculty of Fine and Applied Art, and College of Nursing and Health. The sample groups used in this study are selected randomly by stratified sampling system. The Yamane formula is applied with an error under 0.05 to calculate and evaluate the groups. From the calculation, 214 teachers and 380 students were selected. The duration of the study was from September 10th to 30th, 2012.

The purpose of this research was to investigate and analyze students and staff's behaviour in the utilization of the news clipping on-line database at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, and to find out the problems.

III. RESULTS OF THIS EXPERIMENT

The descriptive statistics is used to investigate and analyze students and staff's behaviour in the utilization of the news clipping on-line database at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, and to find out the problems. It is shown as Tables I to III.

TABLE I
 THE PERCENTAGES OF STUDENTS AND STAFF'S BEHAVIOUR IN ACCESS TO THE ONLINE NEWS CLIPPING DATABASE AT SUAN SUNANDHA RAJABHAT UNIVERSITY

Type of access	N	Percentages
1. Access time (more than 1 answer)		
1.2 Everyday.	74	11.46
1.2 One time per week.	116	17.96
1.3 2-3 times per week.	134	20.74
1.4 one time per month	137	21.21
1.5 2-3 times per month	65	10.06
1.6 One time per semester	124	19.2
1.7 2-3 times per semester	96	14.86
1.8 others	0	0
Total	646	100
2. Access source (more than 1 answer)		
2.1 Friends	298	37.53
2.2 SARC website	286	36.02
2.3 SARC user's guide	38	4.79
2.4 SARC orientation	44	5.54
2.5 Teacher	62	7.81
2.6 Librarian	49	6.17
2.7 e-document	17	2.14
Total	794	100
3. Access way (more than 1 answer)		
3.1 Training of SARC	176	27.46
3.2 SARC access guide	89	13.88
3.3 themselves	224	34.95
3.4 Librarian recommendation	98	15.29
3.5 Friends recommendation	54	8.42
3.6 other	0	0
Total	641	100
4. Access place (more than 1 answer)		
4.1 SARC	79	13.14
4.2 Department	198	32.95
4.3 Home	324	53.91
4.4 Others	0	0
Total	601	100

From Table I, the behaviour of the SSRU students and staff in access to the online news clipping database, reveals that most users know the online news clipping service from their friends (37.53%), library's web site (36.02%) and their teachers (7.81%). The users learn how to use it by themselves (34.95%) and others learned by training of SSRU library (27.46%). Most users used the online news clipping database one time per month (21.21%) at home (53.91%).

Fig. 1 The result of the percentages students and staff in access to the online news clipping database at SSRU

TABLE II
 THE PERCENTAGES OF STUDENTS AND STAFF'S BEHAVIOUR IN THE UTILIZATION OF THE ONLINE NEWS CLIPPING DATABASE AT SUAN SUNANDHA RAJABHAT UNIVERSITY

The purpose of utilization	The Benefit Level					
	Most	Benefit	Averagely Benefit	Rarely Benefit	Least Benefit	No Benefit at All
1.1 Use for general knowledge	37.8	35.0	19.5	7.7	0	0
1.2 use for up-to-date academic knowledge	22.7	50.3	16.6	0	0	10.2
1.3 use as assignment reference	20.7	35.5	34.5	9.2	0	0
1.4 use as teaching material	17.6	14.9	3.3	0	0	63.9
1.5 use as research reference	19.5	20.3	17.3	0	0	42.7
1.6 use for writing books, essay and academic creation	14.9	3.2	6.57	9.2	0	65.9
1.7 use for work and operation	13.9	3.3	5.39	0	0	7

From Table II, it is found that the purpose of utilization at the most benefit level are using for knowledge (37.8%), and for work and operation (13.9%). Moreover, the purpose of utilization at no benefit at all level are using for writing books, essay and academic creation (65.9%), using as teaching material (63.9%), and using as research reference (42.7%).

Fig. 2 The result of the student's and staff's behavior in the utilization of the online news clipping database at most benefit and no benefit

Fig. 3 The result of the problems of online news clipping using of the students and staff

TABLE III
THE PROBLEM OF ONLINE NEWS CLIPPING DATABASE'S UTILIZATION OF STUDENTS AND STAFF

Type of Problem	Problem rate		
	\bar{X}	S.D.	Evaluation
1. Service management	4.23	0.62	High
2. Service device: computer, tools and network	4.12	0.48	High
3. Users themselves	4.29	0.54	High
4. Service provider	4.22	0.64	High
5. Publicity	4.02	0.70	High
Total	4.18	0.60	High

From Table III, it is found that the highest problem of online news clipping database's utilization is users themselves ($\bar{x}=4.29$, S.D. = 0.54), while the lowest problem is publicity. ($\bar{x}=4.02$, S.D. = 0.70)

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, the research results are divided into 2 parts by the research purposes;

A. The Students and Staff's Behaviour towards the Utilization of the Online News Clipping Database

It is found that the behaviour of the SSRU students and staff towards the utilization of the online news clipping database are in access of the online news clipping database revealed that, most users know the online news clipping service from their friends, the library's web site and their teachers. The users learn how to use it by themselves and others learn from training of SSRU library. Most users use the online news clipping database one time per month at home. They use the database for knowledge, and for work and operation at most benefit level on purpose. Moreover, the purpose of utilization at no benefit at all level are using in writing books, essay and academic creation, using as teaching material, and using as research reference.

B. The Problem of the Online News Clipping Database's Utilization

The problems of using the online news clipping service are users themselves, service management, service device: computer and tools; and network, service provider, and publicity.

However, the above results show the preliminary information that would be beneficial for librarians and teachers for planning and designing of library services in their works and organization. In future work, researching about model to promote the online news clipping services for users at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University should be conducted.

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